

A Simple SPICE Modeling Strategy for Common-Mode Chokes

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Abstract

common-mode chokes (CMCs) are commonly used in power converters to filter out noise components from polluting the environment, either on DC or AC side. Having an accurate way to describe them inside circuitual model enables the evaluation of complex systems and to early estimate filter effectiveness. This paper describes a simple way to model CMCs in SPICE simulators able to produce accurate simulations without slowing down simulation as other solutions do. This methodology has been used to model commercial CMCs and compare with their datasheets, showing good adherence with simulation and real measurements.

1 Introduction

CMCs are passive components used to create a high impedance at a given frequency in order to be an obstacle at the propagation of unwanted signals (typically *electro-magnetic* (EM) noise). The structure is the same of a wound inductor: there is a nucleus made of ferromagnetic material and one or more cables wound onto this core. The difference lays on the type of core chosen for this application, indeed:

- they have a poor quality factor above few tens of MHz, i.e., they are selected to introduce as much loss as possible;
- their resulting inductance is intentionally kept low;
- they absorb energy and convert it into heat.

Depending on the kind of material used, the choke resulting can operate at different frequencies. Iron-powder cores are active at low frequency ($f_c < 10$ MHz), manganese-zinc ones operates at higher frequencies (between 20 MHz and 80 MHz), and nickel-zinc cores are suitable for even higher frequencies ($f_c > 60$ MHz) [1], [2]. These materials are perfectly suitable for noise generated in the MHz range. In case of power electronics, when

main noise contribution is generated at lower frequency (i.e., $10 \div 100$ kHz), another class of material has an important role: nanocrystalline cores [3]–[6]. These materials are created by rapidly cooling down melted alloys composed of iron, boron, silicon, and others elements. The thermal shock creates an amorphous structure with peculiar characteristics:

- high permeability,
- low coercivity,
- wide frequency range, and
- superior stability in temperature.

Obviously these superior characteristics come in price of higher cost.

Depending on the target application, choosing the appropriate material can bring to high advantages in terms of choke effectiveness. Typically these chokes are tested on the final equipment in order to understand which is the best for system's need, but this can introduce delays in the design and production process. For this reason, simulating these devices in advance to compare different materials and manufacturers becomes important to anticipate issues that can be found only in the final setup.

Since long time, one of the simplest and effective way to model electronic circuits is to use SPICE

simulators. In the last years it has been used to build simple, but accurate models for study of noise propagation paths in power electronics [7]–[9]. For this reason including a realistic model of a choke into a SPICE description can help investigating filter properties and its ability to make the system compatible with *electro-magnetic compatibility* (EMC) norms [10], [11]. Unfortunately CMCs are non-linear devices and strongly vary their impedance with frequency. To correctly simulate this non-linear behavior there are several possibilities reported by literature:

- using dependent sources, based on physics phenomena [12];
- including frequency dependence in some of the passive elements used to model the choke [13];
- implementing multi-stage passive networks able to mimic real device behavior [14].

Unfortunately all these solutions are increasing model complexity and thus the simulation time. Since a complete electric traction system contains lots of components (i.e., inverters, batteries, motors. . .) and their couplings to the surrounding environment, keeping each part as simple as possible is crucial to limit model complexity and hence simulation time. The approach presented in this paper is a very simple and straightforward way to model CMC that offers realistic impedance behavior in frequency, maintaining a very simple circuitual implementation.

The paper is organized as follows: section 2 describes the model strategy we propose and section 3 the simple algorithm that allow us to get modeling parameters from impedance curves; section 4 shows some examples of the usage of this modeling strategy applied to commercial components; section 5 compares simulation results with measurements on real devices. We draw some final conclusions in section 6.

2 A Simple Modeling Strategy

Typical impedance of ferromagnetic material is shown in Fig. 1. It starts at low frequency with a low value, increases with variable slope (inductive zone), then saturates to a given value (resistive

Fig. 1: Typical impedance for inductors/choles.

Fig. 2: Comparison among different methods to model choke impedance: green line is the impedance of an ideal inductor, red line the one of a realistic inductor, and blue line the one of a CMC.

zone), and finally drops back to low value for frequencies above its usage band (capacitive zone).

The simplest model for a CMC is an inductor, since it has an impedance that increases with frequency, but it is at a constant rate. Even adding some stray parameters, like winding to winding capacitance and DC resistance will not produce great benefits, Fig. 2 shows. For this reason we tried to introduce non-linear behavior of this component into a simple SPICE representation.

The idea we had was to combine several inductances to shape the global frequency response matching the impedance of the ferrite under analysis. To make the model automatically selecting which inductance to use at a given frequency, we inserted a resistor in series to each inductor to create

Fig. 3: How choke impedance is approximated using parallel R-L branches.

an R-L circuit: before the crossover frequency it behaves like a simple resistor and afterwards operates like an inductor. Putting several stages of these R-L networks in parallel and choosing component values appropriately we can mimic the behavior of a real CMC (Fig. 3).

The idea behind this approach is to activate in sequence one branch at a time (actually at a given frequency, corresponding to the point which the inductance has been measured) and make the active stages producing the desired impedance. Obviously this works only if crossover frequencies of R-L branches are far enough in frequency form each other. This is not always the case, but in section 3 we describe how to cope with this limitation.

These networks are easy to dimension since they can derive directly from datasheets, where inductance of the choke is reported at various frequencies. To ease even more this process we develop a simple algorithm and we implemented on a spreadsheet. Section 3 details this part.

Last note it worth to mention is related to the simulator used. Even if this approach might seem simplistic, typically materials used for CMC show a monotonic behavior in the range of conducted emission (i.e., between 150 kHz and 30 MHz [10] or 108 MHz [11]).

All simulations for this paper have been done using LTspice simulator [15], but all the concepts shown are perfectly applicable inside other commercial SPICE-based software.

3 Model Identification

3.1 Calculating Model Parameters

The model described in previous section is based on parallel R-L branches reproducing behavior of choke impedance in frequency.

The value of these components can be found by applying this simple algorithm:

1. The resistance in common to all branches is the DC resistance of the choke

$$R_0 = R_{DC} \quad (1)$$

2. The first element pair is calculated as follows

$$L_1 = L_m(f_1) \quad (2)$$

$$R_1 = 2\pi f_1 L_1 / \sqrt{2} \quad (3)$$

where: L_1 and R_1 are the value to be found; $L_m(f_1)$ is the inductance value at the desired frequency, either provided by the datasheet or by direct measurements; f_1 is the frequency at which we want to approximate the impedance.

3. To find the value for next elements, we have to compute the equivalent inductance of the other branches at the frequency we are interested in

$$L_i = \frac{L_{e,i-1} \cdot L_{m,i}}{L_{e,i-1} - L_{m,i}} \quad (4)$$

$$R_i = 2\pi f_1 L_i / \sqrt{2} \quad (5)$$

where: $L_{e,i-1}$ is the equivalent inductance of previously calculated branches (at lower frequencies); $L_{m,i}$ is the desired inductance.

The same will apply for the following branches, but at each new branch added, the impedance to be used is the equivalent resistance of the previous branches. Since all the branches are present in any time and they are influencing each others, several refining iterations might be necessary.

The number of elements to use depends on the level of accuracy we want to achieve and from how complex is the inductance behavior in frequency, section 3.2 provides some insight of how it can be determined.

As can be noticed, the approach shown is perfectly independent from the software used and can be

adapted not only to SPICE-like simulators. Moreover it can be used to model any impedances variable in frequency, not only chokes (i.e., ferrites, inductors...).

3.2 Number of Stages

Determining the appropriate number of stages to get the best model can be done in several ways:

1. manually by looking at impedance function in frequency; it's easy to identify slope changes and to put a segment for each different segment;
2. describing the scenario as an optimization problem and using iterative search to find the optimum.

From our experience with few number of stages (i.e., 3-4) we can model in an accurate way most of the chokes we used. Nevertheless, since we use these devices into models describing very complex systems (i.e., electric traction system) with assumptions hard to model in an accurate way, even introducing differences between the the simulation model and the real device is typically not invalidating the analysis. For these reasons, we have never had the need for implementing an optimization algorithm to get reasonable results from our models.

Another point it worth to mention is related to the mutual interactions among stages. As far as each stage has a crossover frequency at least one decade far from the others, the interactions among the stages are negligible. Otherwise adding stages will make the model inaccurate because over-defined. A good approach to detect when these phenomena become evident is to monitor the effect a new stage has on the impedance of the rest of the model. If adding a new stage makes any of the components negative in value, this means we are over-defining the model and hence we can intervene by removing unnecessary branches.

3.3 Multiple Conductors

Our model strategy, as the one proposed by [14], is easily adaptable to multi-port implementation, i.e., depending on the number of conductors passing through the core. Once the core has been modeled for the artificial case of a single wire, we can easily adapt the model to the N -conductors case by

- N -plicating the network synthesized for the single conductor case;
- coupling the inductors with the same time constant using an ideal coefficient (i.e., $K = 1$);
- multiplying each resistor value by the number of conductors.

Fig. 4 provides an example of a commercial device modeled in various configurations, i.e., as single conductor (implementing a simple cable ferrite), as dual conductor (suitable for modeling DC-side CMC), and as triple conductor (for three-phase chokes).

4 Simulations

Using the approach proposed in previous sections we modeled several chokes, we simulated their insertion loss behavior, then we compared datasheet-extracted frequency-dependent impedance behavior of each of them against the SPICE model to highlight differences between datasheet and our model.

We selected two very different devices: one Ni-Zn toroid from *Würth Electronics* (WE) (74270097 [16]) and a nanocrystalline toroid from Vacuum-schmelze (L2063-W627 [17]). Please, note that these devices are suitable for usage at different frequencies, hence datasheets are providing impedance data at different frequency regions.

For the first device (74270097) we used a two-turn configuration, to improve the impedance at low frequency, Fig. 5 reports the expected behavior (dashed line) and the simulation model (solid line). It is immediate to see an almost perfect matching between the two up to 200 MHz.

The other device (L2063-W627) has been used in a single-turn configuration (expected to be used on a bus bar setup). Figure 6 shows the comparison between expected impedance and the model. Even in this case adherence between the model and the datasheet is very good.

Looking at higher frequencies these model does not match accurately the expected behavior, but it is expected since we use only R-L branches, hence the impedance can change its slope, but can only have a monotonic increase. To introduce an impedance

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4: An example where the same core is modeled with multiple wire configurations: single conductor (a), dual conductor (b), and triple conductor (c).

drop, as shown in the devices under consideration, we have to introduce one or more capacitive branches in parallel. Typically this causes an improved impedance matching at higher frequency, but degrades the accordance in the band of our interest, for this reason we are not covering the topic in this paper.

5 Measurements

To verify the accuracy of our model we decided to perform some measurements on real devices and to compare their impedance with the one estimated using SPICE. For this task we used a *vector network analyzer* (VNA) from SIGLENT (SVA1032X [18]), suitable for measurements between 100 kHz and 3.2 GHz.

We started characterizing the behavior of WE's 74270097 device single winding, two turns. This device is suitable for high frequency disturbance, since its datasheet is providing data above 1 MHz. Figure 5b shows on the same graph the impedance provided by the datasheet, the simulation our model produces, and measurements on the real device. All the three are aligned between 5 MHz and 400 MHz. At higher frequencies we were expecting the real device to be aligned with the datasheet, instead we find more similarities with our model. This probably because of the fixture (Fig. 7) we used for device characterization that includes some inductance at high frequency. At lower frequencies, measurements are showing an impedance far below the expectation, but we do not have an explanation for this behavior.

The other choke we took into account is L2063-W627 from Vacuumschmelze. In this case the device is more suitable for low frequencies due to the type of material used. Figure 6b shows the behavior of the real component and compares it with our SPICE model and the datasheet. In the range between 300 kHz and 30 MHz the model shows a good matching with real measurements. Unfortunately the other interesting zone (between 10 kHz and 100 kHz) is not shown since the VNA is limited to 100 kHz as lower frequency. The fixture used in this case is the same as the other core, but the stray inductance is not producing visible effect in the band of interest.

The models shown have been built on information extracted from the datasheets, but to make them

more realistic we could refine them by using data coming from the characterization of real devices.

6 Conclusion

This paper presented a simple approach to model common-mode chokes in SPICE-compatible simulators. The approach exploits multiple R-L branches in parallel to shape the impedance as expected. The algorithm to dimension these branches is straightforward and it is based on the impedance shown by the branch at the cut-off frequency.

In our case we based our analysis on CMC, but this methodology can be applied to generic non-linear components and can be easily used for inductors with ferromagnetic core. This model has been easily adapted to model chokes with multiple windings by simply N -plicating the description, adding coupling among inductors, and multiplying by N each resistor value.

We compared the impedance reported by the datasheet with the one simulated with SPICE and we saw a good accordance between the two graphs in the range where conducted emissions are evaluated. The same has been done with measurement on real devices, showing very similar behavior for a pretty wide frequency range. In case the difference between real device and simulation model are too high, the model can be refined using data coming from device characterization.

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References

- [1] P. Hillenbrand, S. Tenbohlen, C. Keller, and K. Spanos, "Understanding conducted emissions from an automotive inverter using a common-mode model," in *2015 IEEE International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC)*, 2015, pp. 685–690. DOI: 10.1109/ISEMC.2015.7256246.
- [2] T. Brander, A. Gerfer, B. Rall, and H. Zenkner, *Trilogy of Magnetics: Design Guide for EMI filter design, SMP & RF circuits*. Würth Electronics, 2010.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5: Comparison of WE's 74270097 impedance as reported by device datasheet (gray line), our SPICE model (orange line), and measurement on real device (blue line).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6: Comparison of Vacuumschmelze's L2063-W627 impedance as reported by device datasheet (gray line), our SPICE model (orange line), and measurement on real device (blue line).

Fig. 7: Fixture used to perform toroid characterization.

- [3] A. Roch and F. Leferink, "Nanocrystalline Core Material for High-Performance Common Mode Inductors," *Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, vol. 54, no. 4, Aug. 2012.
- [4] R. Klinger and J. Beichler, "Nanocrystalline Materials for the Next Generation of Noise Suppression Solutions," *Magnetics Business & Technology Magazine*, 2013.
- [5] J. Petzold, "Advantages of Softmagnetic Nanocrystalline Materials for Modern Electronic Applications," *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, 2002.
- [6] G. T. Nikolov and V. C. Valchev, "Nanocrystalline magnetic materials versus ferrites in power electronics," *Procedia Earth and Planetary Science*, 2009.
- [7] D. N. Dalal, N. Christensen, A. B. Jorgensen, J. K. Jorgensen, S. Beczkowski, *et al.*, "Impact of power module parasitic capacitances on medium-voltage sic mosfets switching transients," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 298–310, 2020. DOI: 10.1109/JESTPE.2019.2939644.
- [8] N. Christensen, A. B. Jorgensen, D. Dalal, S. D. Sonderskov, S. Beczkowski, *et al.*, "Common mode current mitigation for medium voltage half bridge sic modules," in *2017 19th European Conference on Power Electronics and Applications (EPE'17 ECCE Europe)*, 2017, P.1–P.8. DOI: 10.23919/EPE17ECCEurope.2017.8099202.
- [9] A. B. Jorgensen, N. Christensen, D. N. Dalal, S. D. Sonderskov, S. Beczkowski, *et al.*, "Reduction of parasitic capacitance in 10 kv sic mosfet power modules using 3d fem," in *2017 19th European Conference on Power Electronics and Applications (EPE'17 ECCE Europe)*, 2017, P.1–P.8. DOI: 10.23919/EPE17ECCEurope.2017.8098962.
- [10] International Electrotechnical Commission, "Information technology equipment — Radio disturbance characteristics — Limits and methods of measurement," International Electrotechnical Commission, Standard, 2008.
- [11] —, "Vehicles, boats and internal combustion engines — Radio disturbance characteristics — Limits and methods of measurement for the protection of on-board receivers," International Electrotechnical Commission, Standard, 2016.
- [12] F. Sixdenier, O. Yade, C. Martin, A. Bréard, and C. Vollaie, "How to include frequency dependent complex permeability Into SPICE models to improve EMI filters design?" *AIP Advances*, vol. 8, no. 5, p. 056604, 2018. DOI: 10.1063/1.5004630. eprint: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5004630>.
- [13] Coilcraft. "Using Coilcraft models in LTSpice." (), [Online]. Available: <https://www.coilcraft.com/en-us/models/howto/using-coilcrafts-models-in-ltspice/>.
- [14] I. Stevanovic, S. Skibin, M. Masti, and M. Laitinen, "Behavioral Modeling of Chokes for EMI Simulations in Power Electronics," *Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 28, no. 2, 2013.
- [15] G. Brocard, *The LTSpice IV Simulator: Manual, methods and applications*. Wurth Electronics, 2013.
- [16] Wurth Elektronik. "74270097: We-tof emi suppression toroidal ferrite." (), [Online]. Available: <https://www.we-online.com/>.
- [17] Vacuumschmelze. "L2063-W627 Specification for Soft Magnetic Cores." (), [Online]. Available: <https://www.vacuumschmelze.com/>.
- [18] SIGLENT Technologies Co.Ltd. "SVA1000X Series Spectrum Analyzer User Manual." (), [Online]. Available: <https://www.siglent.eu/>.